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The value of diagnostic laparoscopy in chronic peritonitis of unknown origin

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Abstract

Background: The etiology of chronic peritonitis remains some times undetermined and laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis are not specific nor diagnostic. Anti-tuberculosis therapeutic trial some times justified. The aim of this study is to determine the diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases,

Patients and Methods: Forty patients, 15 males (37.5%) and 25 females (62.5%) with chronic peritonitis were admitted from December 1995 to June 1999 at the Gastroenterology center of Baghdad teaching Hospital. The origin of peritonitis remained unknown as laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis showed non specific findings. Their mean age was 37.5 year. 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination.

The patients were studied retrospectively and prospectively to determine the possible diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases

Results: The maximum age incidence of the patients was between 20-39 years (52.5%) Abdominal distension and abdominal pain were the commonest presenting symptoms. Abdominal distension and tenderness were the

commonest abdominal signs. 9 patients (22.5%) have of pulmonary abnormalities and pleural effusion. 3 patients (7.5 %) have diabetes and one patient have cirrhosis. of the 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination: ascites with bowel and peritoneal adhesions were present in 18 patients (50%), ascites with multiple whitish nodules and omental thickening in 12 patients (33.3%), bowel thickening with visceral adhesions without ascites in 2 patients (5.5%), female reproductive organs involvement with peritoneal nodules in 2 patients (5.5%), and peritoneal nodules with hepatic involvement in 2 patients (5.5%).

Conclusion: The laparoscopic findings were non specific and the procedure is of no diagnostic value.

Introduction

The etiology of chronic peritonitis remains some times undetermined and laboratory tests including ascetic fluid analysis are not specific nor did diagnostic. Anti-tuberculosis therapeutic trial some times justify. The aim of this study is to determine the diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases.

Patients and Methods: Forty patients, 15 males (37.5%) and 25 females (62.5%) with chronic peritonitis were admitted from December 1995 to June 1999 at the Gastroenterology center of Baghdad teaching Hospital. The origin of peritonitis remained unknown as laboratory tests including ascitic fluid analysis showed non specific findings. Their mean age was 37.5 year. 36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination. The patients were studied retrospectively and prospectively to determine the possible diagnostic value of laparoscopy in such cases

.24 patients (60%) were living in Baghdad, 9 patients (22.5%) were living in the North of Iraq and 7 patients (17.5%) were living in the south of Iraq.

Results: The maximum age incidence of the patients was between 20-39 years (52.5%)The presenting symptom was abdominal distension in 29 patients(72.5%),abdominal pain in 15(37.5%) patients, fever in 8(20%) patients, jaundice in 5(12%) patients, weight loss in 4(10%) patients ,abdominal mass in 1 patient, acute abdomen in 1 patient, and generalize weakness in 1 patient.15 patients (37.5%) presented within 1 month or less from the start of symptom.23 patients (55.5%) were symptomatic for 2-6 months before presentation ,and 2 patients(5%) have symptoms for more than 7 months on presentation. On examination 37 patients (92.5%) have abdominal distension,38 patients (95%) have peritonitis,37 (92.5%) have generalized wasting,27(67.5%) have fever,21 patients(52.5%) have abdominal tenderness,9 patients(22.5%) have heaptomegaly ,8 patients (20%) have heatosplenomegaly.3 patients (7.5%) have abdominal mass, 3 patients

(7.5%) have jaundice, and 1 patient have axillary lymphadenopathy. 9 patients (22.5%) have of pulmonary changes, and pleural effusion.3 patients (7.5%) have diabetes and one patient have cirrhosis.

Abdominal ultrasound showed ascitic fluid in 33 patients (82.5%),organomegaly (heaptomegaly with or without splenomegaly) in 18 patients (45%),peritoneal adhesion and bowel thickening in 9 patients (22.5%),abdominal mass in 3 patients (7.5%),and abdominal lymph node enlargement in one patient.36 patients undergone laparoscopic examination:ascites with bowel and peritoneal adhesions were present in 18 patients (50%),ascites with multiple whitish nodules and omental thickening in 12 patients(33.3%),bowel thickening with visceral adhesions without ascites in 2 patients (5.5%),female reproductive organs involvement with peritoneal nodules in 2 patients (5.5%),and peritoneal nodules with hepatic involvement in 2 patients (5.5%).

Discussion: The laparoscopic findings in this study were similar to laparoscopic finding in patients with TB peritonitis [1]; however these findings are neither specific nor diagnostic. The diagnostic laparoscopy in patients with chronic peritonitis of unknown origin is unlikely to be of significant value as the findings are largely non specific. Continued follow up of such patients could more helpful in such cases.

References

1-Rodreigues de Lope C, San Miguel.Laprosopical diagnosis of tuberculosis ascites.Endoscopy 1982; 14(5):178-179.